

SuMu

Methodology for Assessing the Socio-Economic Impact of Large Cultural and Sporting Events. The SuMu Model

What is SuMu?

SuMu is an Excel-based digital tool designed to assess the socio-economic impact of cultural and sporting events in Estonia that have international significance. It is a predictive model that enables the evaluation of the impact of various potential and actual events organized in Estonia on the host municipality, Estonia, event organizers and other stakeholders.

Who is the SuMu model intended for, and what is its purpose?

The primary users of SuMu are expected to be government agencies, local municipalities, and event organizers. Organizers can use it to forecast the overall impact and profitability of their events, while government agencies and municipalities can apply the model to make decisions related to the provision of financial support. Thus, the main objective of the model is to enable both the public and private sectors to make better decisions when bringing large events to Estonia and ensuring their profitability. The model is particularly applicable to large events with 2,000 to 50,000 attendees.

What does SuMu measure?

SuMu measures the socio-economic impacts of events. This includes the economic impact generated by event attendance, the social impact on the residents of the host municipality, and the long-term economic effects resulting from an improved image, which could attract more visitors in the future. Visitors are often not just influenced by the event itself but also contribute economically by paying for accommodation, dining, and engaging with the local community in various ways during their stay.

How was SuMu developed?

The theoretical foundation and structure of the SuMu model were created based on previous academic literature and models that address the different types of impacts of events and tourism worldwide. The theoretical relationships were quantified using data collected during the pilot phase of 10 sports and 10 cultural events, as well as from previous studies.

What problem does SuMu help to solve?

A region's image plays an essential role in attracting visitors, but its impact is difficult to measure financially. While SuMu cannot precisely quantify the long-term economic impact of image (and this should be considered more of a magnitude estimate), it is, to the authors' knowledge, the first model that attempts to measure this across different types of events. Additionally, SuMu is predictive and specifically tailored to work in the context of Estonia.